

Prevalence of Depression and Anxiety and their Associated Factors in Patients Attending Palliative Care Centre

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Abstract:

Background: Palliative care patients are vulnerable to a range of psychological and mental health problems, including depression and anxiety. The patient usually undergoes various stages of treatment before reaching the Palliative care Centre. A variety of factors related to the cancer and its treatment are likely to impact on the development of depression and anxiety, including the type of cancer, stage and prognosis. The present cross-sectional study was planned to estimate the prevalence of depression and anxiety and to assess the associated factors in patients attending palliative care center, SMS Jaipur.

Aim: To screen patients with various malignancies for the presence of depressive and anxiety disorders using standardized rating scales.

Materials & Methods: Five hundred and twenty-seven (n = 527) patients admitted in the Palliative Care Centre, SMS Hospital, Jaipur were included in the study who completed the Patient Health Questionnaire-9 and Generalized Anxiety Disorder-7 (GAD-7) Questionnaire.

Results: Out of 527 patients, majority of patients (73.06%; n=385) were suffering from one or more psychiatric co-morbidity in the form of either isolated anxiety or depression or both. 31.5% had both anxiety and depression, 26.57% had only depression and 14.99% had only anxiety. In 46.49% cases anxiety was present (GAD score ≥ 8). Prevalence of anxiety was more in younger population i.e. ≤ 40 years (48.25%, n=55), rural population (52.74%, n=154), patients with advanced or metastatic stage of malignancy (54.19%; n=168), patients receiving multiple modalities (53.81%) of treatment were more likely to suffer from anxiety followed by those receiving radiotherapy (45.71%) and chemotherapy (41.58%). In 58.06% cases depression was present with PHQ score ≥ 10 , the mean age of cases having depression was 50.60 years. Prevalence of depression was more in rural population (65.75%, n=192), patients from lower socioeconomic status (60.56%, n=261), patients with advanced or metastatic stage of malignancy (65.16%; n=202), patients receiving multiple modalities (86.02%, n=203) of treatment were more likely to suffer from depression followed by those receiving radiotherapy (48.57%, n=17) and chemotherapy (41.58%, n=42).

Conclusion: Compared to the general population, the prevalence of anxiety and depression is often higher among people with cancer, but estimates vary due to a number of factors, such as demographic factors (age, sex, residence, socioeconomic status), the type of cancer, stage of cancer and received treatment.

Keywords: depression, anxiety, cancer, palliative care, malignancy.

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Introduction

Palliative care patients are vulnerable to a range of psychological and mental health problems, including Depression and Anxiety. A variety of factors related to the cancer and its treatment are likely to impact on the development of depression and anxiety, including the type of cancer, stage and prognosis. The prevalence of anxiety and depression is often higher among people with cancer, but estimates vary due to a number of factors. Depending upon the diagnostic criteria used the rates of de-

pression could range from 3–69% among the patients in Palliative care center in various studies. [1,2] Individual risk factors that may increase the risk of depression, similar to the general population, include demographic factors, such as age and gender, and social and economic factors such as unemployment, fewer educational qualifications and a lack of social support. [3] A variety of factors related to the cancer and its treatment are likely to impact on the development of depression and anxi-

ety, including the type of cancer, stage and prognosis. Cancer treatments including immunotherapy and chemotherapy may induce depression through particular biological mechanisms, such as inflammatory pathways, and some medications used to treat chemotherapy-induced nausea can reduce dopaminergic transmission, which is implicated in the development of depressive symptoms. The development of depression and anxiety among people with cancer is also likely to depend on factors at the structural level, including healthcare costs and access, as well as access to welfare support, such as disability benefits, as cancer can have a significant financial impact. Several psychological factors are also important. [4] Untreated psychiatric morbidities among patients attending Palliative care center can significantly impact morbidity, lead to poor adherence to treatment, longer and more frequent hospitalizations, contribute to poor prognosis, poor quality of life, and lead to increased mortality. The present cross-sectional study was planned to estimate the prevalence of depression and anxiety and to assess the associated factors in patients attending palliative care center, SMS Jaipur.

Materials and Methods

The study was approved by the Ethics Committee of the Institute, and all the patients were recruited after obtaining written informed consent. Five hundred and twenty seven (n = 527) patients were recruited among patients admitted in the Palliative Care Centre, SMS Hospital, Jaipur. To be included in the study, the patients were required to be aged between 18-80 years, newly registered in palliative care and have a biopsy proven malignancy. Patients those known to have diagnosed psychiatric illness before be diagnosed with malignancy, patients with preexisting severe cognitive impairment, and patients who were drug abusers and alcoholics were excluded from the study. Participants completed the questionnaires themselves.

Instruments

Patient Health Questionnaire-9: Patient health Questionnaire-9 (PHQ-9) was used to assess depression. It is a self-report questionnaire, which comprises nine items, each evaluating the nine Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders-Fifth Edition criteria of depression, rated as "0" (not at all) to "3" (nearly every day). PHQ-9 has been shown to be a valid instrument to diagnose depression, having high sensitivity (61%) and specificity (94%) for diagnosing depression in adults. PHQ-9 score ≥ 10 has a sensitivity of 88% and a specificity of 88% for the diagnosis of major depression made by a mental health profession. In the present study, we used the cutoff of ≥ 10 for making the diagnosis of depression.

Generalized Anxiety Disorder-7 Scale: It is a seven-item scale to assess anxiety. It has been

shown to have good reliability as well as criterion, construct, factorial, and procedural validity. Cutoff points of 5, 10, and 15 are interpreted as representing mild, moderate, and severe levels of anxiety on the Generalized Anxiety Disorder-7 (GAD-7). However, the diagnostic threshold has been reported to be a cutoff score of ≥ 8 . There is good agreement between self-report and interviewer-administered versions of the scale. In the present study, a cutoff score of 8 or more was used to make the diagnosis of GAD.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 16. Statistical test were carried out with univariate, bivariate and multivariable analysis. For univariate analysis, descriptive analysis was used while for bivariate analysis, Chi-square test and Correlation test were used. For paired samples t-test was applied to compare the mean score difference of baseline and follow-up anxiety and depression. P- Value < 0.05 is considered as statistically significant.

Results

Five hundred and twenty seven (n=527) patients admitted in the Palliative care center completed the questionnaires. The mean age of patients was 51.20 years with majority of patients were above 40 years (78.37%). There were 65.09% males and 34.91% female with male: female ratio is 1.86:1. Majority (86.15%) were Hindu cases followed by 13.28% Muslims and 0.57% were Others. Majority (96.39%) were married, were from rural area (55.41%), from nuclear family (67.17%) and were literate (66.79%). In terms of socioeconomic status, according to modified Kuppaswamy scale, majority (81.78%) were from lower class. Majority of cases (45.35%) caregiver was Son/Daughter followed by 16.13% were spouse and 33.97% were others. Most common Malignancies was Oropharyngeal Malignancies (34.16%) followed by 12.14% were having lung cancer, 11.20% had breast cancer other malignancies includes Hepatobiliary Malignancies (8.16%), Gynecological Malignancies (6.83%), Gastrointestinal Malignancies (6.45%), Neck Region Malignancies (4.36%), Hematological Malignancies (3.98%), Male Urogenital Malignancies (3.23%), Pancreatic Malignancies (1.90%), Endocrine Malignancies (0.95%), Nasopharyngeal Ca (0.19%) & Other Malignancies (6.45%). Majority (58.82%) had advanced or metastatic malignancy and had received multiple type of treatment (44.78%)(surgery/chemotherapy/radiotherapy) followed by 19.17% who had received only Chemotherapy, 12.33% had undergone Surgery, 6.64% had taken only radiotherapy, and 17.08% had given no Surgery or Adjuvant Therapy.

Psychiatric comorbidity in the study sample

Figure 1:

In our study, majority of patients (73.06%; n=385) were suffering from one or more psychiatric co-morbidity in the form of either isolated anxiety or depression or both. 26.94% (n=142) of patients did not have the above mentioned psychiatric co-morbidity.

Figure 2: Psychiatric Co-morbidity

Here, we have 31.5% cases who had both anxiety and depression, 26.57% had only depression and 14.99% had only anxiety, 26.94% had no anxiety or depression. Results were similar to previous studies [5,6,7]

Anxiety in study sample: Our study showed 46.49% of patients who presented with anxiety had GAD-7 score ≥ 8 whereas 53.51% patients had no anxiety with GAD-7 score < 8 .

Table 1:

Factors		Anxiety		No-anxiety		P value
		N	%	N	%	
Age	Age<50 years (N=215)	108	50.23	107	49.77	<0.1615
	Age \geq 50 years (N=312)	137	43.91	175	56.09	
Gender	Male (n=343)	150	43.73	193	56.27	<0.0830
	Female (n=184)	95	51.63	89	48.37	
Residence	Rural (n=292)	154	52.74	138	47.26	<0.0013
	Urban (n=235)	91	38.72	144	61.28	
Education	Literate (N=352)	161	45.74	191	54.26	<0.6240
	Illiterate (N=175)	84	48.00	91	52.00	
Socioeconomic Status	Lower (N=431)	205	47.56	226	52.44	<0.5599
	Middle (N=83)	35	42.17	48	57.83	
	Upper (N=13)	5	38.46	8	61.54	
Family	Nuclear (n=354)	169	47.74	185	52.26	<0.41
	Joint (n=173)	76	43.93	97	56.07	
Site of malignancy						<0.7391
Stage Of Malignancy	Stage <4 (Locally Advanced) (N=217)	77	35.48	140	64.52	<0.00002

	Stage ≥ 4 (Advanced or metastatic) (N=310)	168	54.19	142	45.81	
Treatment	Chemotherapy (n=101)	42	41.58	59	58.42	<0.043
	Radiotherapy (n=35)	16	45.71	19	54.29	
	Surgery (n=65)	25	38.46	40	61.54	
	Multiple Modalities (N=236)	127	53.81	109	46.19	
	NIL(N=90)	35	38.89	55	61.11	
Caregiver	Parents (N=22)	9	40.91	13	59.09	<0.4118
	Son/Daughter (N=239)	111	46.44	128	53.56	
	Other (N=179)	78	43.58	101	56.42	
	Spouse (N=87)	47	54.02	40	45.98	

In our study, the mean age of cases having anxiety was 51.48 years. There was no statistically significant difference with presence or absence of anxiety on the basis of age (P-value<<0.1615), gender (P-value=0.0830), education of cases (P-value=0.6240), socio-economic status (P-value=0.5599), family type (P-value=0.6321) & caregiver (P-value=0.4118).

In our study, anxiety was more prevalent in endocrine(100%,n=5) followed by Gastrointestinal Malignancies (58.82%,n=20), Gynecological Malignancies (58.33%,n=21), Male Urogenital Malignancies (58.82%,n=10), followed by breast cancer(57.63%,n=34), then Pancreatic malignancies (50%,n=5), then Hepatobiliary Malignancies (41.86%, n=18), then Oropharyngeal Malignancies (40%, n=72), then ca lung(39.06,n=25), then Neck Region Malignancies (39.12%,n=14), then Hematological Malignancies (28.57%,n=6), & Other Malignancies (58.82%,n=20). However the difference

was statistically insignificant (P-value=0.7391). In our study, patients from rural area were more likely to suffer from anxiety (52.74%, n=154) compared to urban population (P-value<0.00001). Patients with advanced or metastatic stage of malignancy (54.19%; n=168) were more likely to suffer from anxiety than the patients with Stage <4 malignancy (35.48%; n=77) (P-value=0.00002). Patients receiving multiple modalities (53.81%) of treatment were more likely to suffer from anxiety followed by those receiving radiotherapy (45.71%) and chemotherapy (41.58%). Prevalence of anxiety in those patients who underwent surgical treatment (38.46%) was comparable to those receiving no surgical or adjuvant therapy (38.89%) (P-value=0.0285).

Depression in study sample: In 58.06% cases depression was present with PHQ-9 score ≥ 10 , and, 41.94% cases depression was absent with PHQ-9 score <10.

Table 2:

Factors		Depression		No-Depression		P value
		N	%	N	N	
Age	<50 years (N=215)	131	60.93	<50 years (N=215)	131	<0.2163
	≥ 50 years (N=312)	175	56.09	≥ 50 years (N=312)	175	
Gender	Male (n=343)	195	56.85	148	43.15	<0.4409
	Female (n=184)	111	60.33	73	39.67	
Residence	Rural (n=292)	192	65.75	100	34.25	<0.00006
	Urban (n=235)	114	48.51	121	51.49	
Education	Literate (N=352)	204	57.95	148	42.05	<0.9580
	Illiterate (N=175)	101	57.71	74	42.29	
Socioeconomic Status	Lower (N=431)	261	60.56	170	39.44	<0.0393
	Middle (N=83)	40	48.19	43	51.81	
	Upper (N=13)	5	38.46	8	61.54	
Family	Nuclear (n=354)	204	57.63	150	42.37	<0.7709
	Joint (n=173)	102	58.96	71	41.04	
Site of Malignancy	Site of malignancy					<0.3150
Stage of Malignancy	Stage <4 (Locally Advanced) (N=217)	104	47.93	113	52.07	<0.00007
	Stage ≥ 4 (Advanced or metastatic) (N=310)	202	65.16	108	34.84	
Treatment	Chemotherapy (n=101)	42	41.58	59	58.42	<0.00001
	Radiotherapy (n=35)	17	48.57	18	51.43	
	Surgery (n=65)	22	33.85	43	66.15	
	Multiple Modalities (N=236)	203	86.02	33	13.98	
	NIL(n=90)	22	24.44	68	75.56	

Caregiver	Parents (N=22)	10	45.45	12	54.55	<0.0332
	Son/Daughter (N=239)	131	54.81	108	45.19	
	Spouse (N=87)	62	71.26	25	28.74	
	Other (N=179)	103	57.54	76	42.46	

The mean age of cases having Depression was 50.60 years. There was no statistically significant difference with presence or absence of Depression on the basis of age (p value<0.2163), gender (P-value<0.4409), education (P-value<0.9580), family type (P-value<0.7709). Depression was more prevalent in pancreatic (80%, n=8) & endocrine (80%, n=5) followed by Oropharyngeal Malignancies (67.22%, n=121) followed by breast cancer (66.10%, n=39) followed by Male Urogenital Malignancies (64.17%, n=11), followed by Gynecological Malignancies (61.11%, n=22), then Neck Region Malignancies (60.87%, n=14), then, Gastrointestinal Malignancies (55.88%, n=19), then ca lung (43.75, n=28), then Hematological Malignancies (33.33%, n=7), then Hepatobiliary Malignancies (32.56%, n=14), & Other Malignancies (52.94%, n=19). However the difference was statistically insignificant (P-value=0.3150).

In our study patients from rural area were more likely to suffer from depression (65.75%, n=192) than the patients from urban area (48.51%; n=114) (P-value=0.00006). Patients from lower socioeconomic status were more likely to suffer from depression (60.56%) followed by middle socioeconomic status (48.19%, n=40) followed by upper socioeconomic status (38.46%, n=5), (P-value=0.0393). Patients with advanced or metastatic stage of malignancy (65.16%; n=202) were more likely to suffer from depression than the patients with Stage <4 malignancy (47.93%; n=104), (P-value= 0.00007). Patients receiving multiple modalities (86.02%, n=203) of treatment were more likely to suffer from depression followed by those receiving radiotherapy (48.57%, n=17) and chemotherapy (41.58%, n=42). Prevalence of anxiety in those patients who underwent surgical treatment (33.85%) was comparable to those receiving no surgical or adjuvant therapy (24.44%), (P-value<0.00001). Patients with spouse as caregiver were more likely to suffer from depression (71.26%, n=103) followed by patients with others as caregiver (57.54%, n=103) followed by patients with son/daughter as caregiver (54.81%, n=131) then patients with parents as caregiver (45.45%, n=10), (P-value=0.0332).

Discussion

In our study, out of total study population psychiatric comorbidity (anxiety/depression or both) was present in 73.06% (n=385) patients. In total study population depression was more prevalent (58.06% cases with PHQ score ≥ 10) than anxiety (46.49% cases anxiety with GAD score ≥ 8), and we also

found that in 31.5% cases both depression and anxiety present, and, in 26.76% both depression and anxiety absent. This high prevalence of psychiatric illness could be because the sample in the present study consisted of cancer patients who were terminally ill, needing palliative care and suffering from a greater severity of pain. Anxiety was more prevalent in endocrine (100%, n=5) followed by Gastrointestinal Malignancies (58.82%, n=20), Gynecological Malignancies (58.33%, n=21), Male Urogenital Malignancies (58.82%, n=10), followed by breast cancer (57.63%, n=34) etc. However the difference was statistically insignificant (P-value =0.7391). Depression was more prevalent in pancreatic (80%, n=8) & endocrine (80%, n=5) followed by Oropharyngeal Malignancies (67.22%, n=121) followed by breast cancer (66.10%, n=39) followed by Male Urogenital Malignancies (64.17%, n=11) etc. However the difference was statistically insignificant (P-value=0.3150).

In our study, We also found that presence or absence of anxiety and depression was affected by residence of cases whether they belong to rural or urban, affected by socioeconomic status, affected by stage of malignancy and also influenced by type of adjuvant therapy.

Among these factors anxiety and depression was more prevalent in rural cases (p-value<0.00001 for anxiety & <0.00006 for depression), more in cases from low socioeconomic status (p-value<0.55 for anxiety & <0.03 for depression) {similar to previous studies[8]}, in advanced stage (p-value<0.00002 for anxiety & <0.00007 for depression) {similar to previous studies[9,10]} and highest in cases which received multiple modality treatment (p-value<0.02 for anxiety & <0.00001 for depression) followed by which undergo chemotherapy followed by radiotherapy, and surgery. Results were similar to previous studies[11,12,13,14]. Thus, these factors were statistically significant in cases having anxiety and depression. Additionally depression was more prevalent in patients with spouse as caregiver (p value<0.0332).

As our study results, rural area residence and Economic status plays an important role in terms of cancer treatments. In this study, patients' economic status was studied to investigate any association between their economic level and psychiatry morbidity. From the findings, most of the patients are not working and have low monthly income less than Rs. 2000 per month. This situation was considered as low living status due to the high living cost in an urban city. Some of the patients were

from other district or state. The cost of transportation and accommodation can be considerably high. As a consequence, majority of the patients claimed that they felt burdened by cancer treatment and the expenses, especially when referring to their economic status. If this feeling is not being treated, it could allow for the occurrence of psychiatric morbidity. Results were similar to previous studies [8]

As our study results, Cancer treatments can also cause depression and anxiety. It may be due to long periods of treatment, repeated hospitalizations, and side-effects such as nausea, vomiting and alopecia. Cancer diagnosis and treatment have been shown to have profound effects on the psychological status of patients [15]. Association between psychiatric disorders and chemotherapy showed that psychiatric disorders increase with a number of chemotherapies. It could be because medications used in chemotherapy can cause neuropsychiatric sequelae. patients with spouse as caregiver were more likely to suffer from depression This result may be due to, spouse as a caregiver had higher level of strain and burden, old age, increased symptom burden with coexistent morbidity in spouse caregiver moreover spouse as a caregiver are more vulnerable for psychiatric comorbidity, all these factors affects patients leading to increased depression [16,17]. Moreover, in our study presence or absence of anxiety and depression was not affected by gender, education, type of family (nuclear or joint), site of malignancy. These factors are statistically non-significant in cases having anxiety and depression.

Conclusion

The mental health of people living with and beyond cancer in its various types and stages is an important and growing research and clinical priority. The prevalence of anxiety and depression is often higher among people with cancer, but estimates vary due to a number of factors, such as the type and stage of cancer. Patients often do not obtain psychological support or treatment. Hence Depression and anxiety are frequently undiagnosed and untreated in these patients attending palliative care, resulting in a significant negative impact on quality of life and disease outcome.

Study clearly shows that low socioeconomic status, having less financial support, advanced stage malignancies and receiving multiple modality treatment including chemotherapy and radiotherapy, were associated with anxiety and depression. Moreover there is a crucial role of caregiver .For managing cancer patients, more care or support should be given to this type of patients as they are at high risk of anxiety and depression. Future research must focus on establishing diagnostically reliable criteria, developing standard instruments for measuring depression, correlating past psychiatric history of depression and anxiety with current

depression, characterizing the causative role of antineoplastic in depression, and identifying biological markers for depression.

Limitations:

1. The psychiatric indicators were evaluated using screening instruments and the psychiatric diagnoses were not confirmed by a trained mental health professional.
2. The study also did not take into account various clinical variables such as time since diagnosis, level of disability due to illness and treatment, and cost of treatment which could also influence the prevalence of psychiatric morbidity.
3. The study also did not evaluate the impact of psychiatric morbidity on the course and outcome of malignancy.

Recommendations:

1. Screening for depression should be carried out in all palliative care patients. Screening is conducted when the initial diagnosis of cancer is made and periodically thereafter as clinically indicated, especially with changes in cancer or treatment status (eg, post treatment, recurrence, or progression), as well as transition to palliative care.
2. Major depression in terminally ill patients is treatable, relieve uncontrolled symptoms, Supportive psychotherapy with patient& family education and judicious use of antidepressant medications should be considered.

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